

QISQARTIRIB AKSLANTIRISH PRINSIPI

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Topologik fazo - bu mavhum to'plamlarning xususiyatlarini, xususan, uzluksizlik va yaqinlashuvga nisbatan tavsiflovchi matematik tushunchadir. U ochiq to'plamlar deb ataladigan kichik to'plamlar to'plamiga ega bo'lgan nuqtalar to'plamidan iborat bo'lib, ular tutilish va yaqinlik bilan bog'liq ma'lum aksiomalarni qondiradi. Ochiq to'plamlar nuqtalar orasidagi uzluksizlik va bog'lanish darajasini belgilaydi. Mohiyatan topologik fazo to'plamning shakli va tuzilishini matematik aniqlash usulidir.

Psevdometrik - bu fazodagi ikki nuqta orasidagi masofani ma'lum xususiyatlar to'plamiga ko'ra matritsaviy funktsiya bo'lgan metrikaning umumlashtirilishidir. Psevdometriya ko'pincha topologiyada qo'llaniladi, bu erda masofa tushunchasi o'rganilayotgan fazoga qarab umumlashtirilishi mumkin.

Ta'rif: $\|\bullet\|$ psevdonorma deyiladi, agarda quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa:

$$1) \quad \|\bullet\| : T_M \rightarrow T_M^+$$

$$2) \quad \forall \lambda \in C, W \in T_M \text{ uchun}$$

$$\|\lambda \cdot W\| \equiv |\lambda| \|W\|$$

$$3) \quad \forall W, Z \in T_M \text{ uchun}$$

$$\|W\| + \|Z\| - \|Z + W\| \geq \theta$$

Agar $W \in T_M$ bo'lsa,

$\|W\| = \sqrt{WW^*}$ deb oladigan bo'lsak, bu psevdonorma bo'ladi.

$$T_M = C^n[m \times m]$$

Quyidagi matritsaviy funksiyalarni qaraymiz.

$$\|Z - W\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Z_i - W_i)(Z_i - W_i)^*}$$

bu yerda $Z = (Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_n)$

$$W = (W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n) \quad Z_i \in \dot{C}[m \times m], W_i \in \dot{C}[m \times m]$$

Yuqoridagi matrisaviy funksiya psevdometrika shartlarini qanoatlantiradi.

Darhaqiqat,

$$1) \|Z - W\| \geq \theta,$$

$$\|Z - W\| = \theta \quad Z=W$$

$$\forall Z, W \in \dot{C}^{*n}[m \times m]$$

2) Ravshanki, simmetriklik sharti bajariladi

$$\|Z - W\| = \|W - Z\|$$

$$\forall Z, W \in \dot{C}^{*n}[m \times m]$$

$\forall Z, W, t$ lar uchun

$$\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (W_k - Z_k)(W_k - Z_k)^*} + \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - W_k)(t_k - W_k)^*} - \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - Z_k)(t_k - Z_k)^*} \geq \theta$$

Shart bajariladi Bu uchburchak tengsizligidir.

Haqiqatdan ham, quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritsak, demak

$$W_k - Z_k = A_k$$

$$t_k - W_k = B_k$$

$$t_k - Z_k = A_k + B_k$$

$$\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n A_k A_k^*} + \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n B_k B_k^*} - \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (A_k + B_k)(A_k + B_k)^*} \geq \theta$$

tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz

Bu tengsizlik quyidagi Koshi-Bunyakovskiy tengsizligining matrisaviy analogidan bevosita kelib chiqadi.

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n A_k A_k^*\right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n B_k B_k^*\right) - \left(\sum_{k=1}^n A_k\right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n A_k A_k^*\right) \sum_{k=1}^n B_k B_k^* - \left(\sum_{k=1}^n A_k B_k\right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n A_k B_k\right)^* \geq \theta$$

$W, Z \in T$.

$\rho(W, Z) = \|W - Z\|$ psevdometrika bo'ladi

Psevdometrik fazoga misollar keltiramiz.

$$Z = (Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m)$$

$$W = (W_1, W_2, \dots, W_m)$$

$$Z_i \in \dot{C}[m \times m], \quad W_i \in \dot{C}[m \times m]$$

$$\rho(W, Z) = \|W - Z\| =$$

$$\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - Z_k)(t_k - W_k)^*} + \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - W_k)(t_k - W_k)^*} - \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - Z_k)(t_k - W_k)^*} \geq 0$$

$$\rho(W, Z) = \|W - Z\| \geq 0, \quad \rho(W, Z) = 0 \quad Z = W$$

$$2) \text{ Ravshanki, } \rho(W, Z) = \rho(Z, W)$$

Ixtiyoriy $Z, W \in T$ simmetriklik sharti bajarildi

3) Uchburchak tengsizligi

Ushbu maqolada $T_M = \dot{C}^n[m \times m]$ fazoda qisqartirib akslantirish prinsipi o'rganilgan.

(T_M, ρ) psevdometrik fazoda o'z o'ziga akslantiruvchi B akslantirish berilgan bo'lsin.

Ta'rif: Agar T_M fazoda olingan ixtiyoriy W, Z nuqtalar uchun

$$\sqrt{\alpha \alpha^*} \rho(W, Z) - \rho(B, BZ) \geq \theta \quad (1)$$

tengsizlikni qanoatlantiradigan shunday α matrisa

$\alpha \in T_M, (I - \alpha \alpha^* > \theta)$ topilsa u holda B akslantirishni qisqartirib akslantirish deyiladi.

1-TEOREMA. Agar B qisqartirib akslantirish bo'lsa, u holda B akslantirish uzluksiz bo'ladi.

Isboti: Aytaylik A nuqta T fazoning ixtiyoriy nuqtasi va $\varepsilon > 0$ bo'lsin.

$$\varepsilon I - \rho(W, Z) > \theta \quad Z \in T_M$$

shartni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha (T_M, ρ) lar uchun (1) tengsizlikka ko'ra quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\rho(BZ, BA) \leq \sqrt{\alpha \alpha^*} \rho(Z, A) < \sqrt{\alpha \alpha^*} \varepsilon < \varepsilon I$$

Bu esa ixtiyoriy A nuqtada B akslantirishning uzluksiz ekanligini isbotlaydi.

Teorema isbot bo'ldi.

Qisqartirib akslantirish prinsipi

2-TEOREMA. (T_M, ρ) to'la psevdometrik fazoda aniqlangan har qanday B qisqartirib akslantirish, yagona qo'zg'almas nuqtaga ega, ya'ni $BZ = Z$ tenglamaning yagona yechimi mavjud.

Isboti: Aytaylik, W_0 -nuqta T_m fazoning ixtiyoriy nuqtasi bo'lsin. Demak,

$W_1 = BW_0$ deb olamiz, u holda $W_2 = BW_1 = B^2W_0$ umuman,

$W_n = AW_{n-1} = A^n W_0$. (2)

Bu ketma ketlikning fundamental ekanligini ko'rsatamiz.

(1) tengsizlik va psevdometrik fazolarning uchburchak tengsizliklaridan ixtiyoriy $m \geq n$ sonlar uchun quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz

$$\rho(W_n, W_m) = \rho(B^n W_0, B^m W_0) \leq (\sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*})^n \rho(W_0, W_{m-n}) \leq \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*}^n \{ \rho(W_0, W_1) + \rho(W_1, W_2) + \dots + \rho(W_{m-n-1}, W_{m-n}) \} \leq \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*}^n (\rho(W_0, W_1) * \{1 + \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*} + (\sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*})^2 + \dots + (\sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*})^{m-n-1}\}) \leq \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*}^n \rho(W_0, W_1) ((1 - \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*})^{-1})$$

Endi α ning $1 - \sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*} > \theta$ bo'lganligi sababli n yetarli katta bo'lganda bu tengsizlikni o'ng tomonini istalgancha kichik qilish mumkin

Demak, $\{W_n\}$ ketma ketlik fundamental bo'ladi va limitga ega bo'ladi.

Bundan $W = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W_n$ deb olamiz. U holda uzluksizlikdan $BW = B \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} BW_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W_{n+1} = W$. Shunday qilib qo'zgalmis nuqta mabjudligi isbotlandi. Bu nuqtaning yagona ekanligini isbotlaymiz. Faraz qilaylik ikkita bo'lsin. $BW = W, BZ = Z$

U holda (1) tengsizlikga ko'ra

$$\sqrt{\alpha\alpha^*}^n \rho(W, Z) - \rho(W, Z) \geq \theta$$

$1 - \alpha\alpha^* > \theta$ ekanligidan $\rho(W, Z) = \theta$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Bundan

$W = Z$ demak yagona ekan.

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